

Glossary

aṅgula	'finger', a unit of linear measure, the breadth of a finger in extent: BK vy 57, 60, 144; DM 80.84-85, 88-89; KI 54.45, 54.46; MC 4.31, 4.33; PI 6.57, 9.80, 9.86, 9.88-91.
aṭṭāla(ka)	watchtower: BK vy 102; PI 8.89, 8.212, 8.224, 8.226, 8.229.
ācārya	the chief officiant: BK vy 10; DM 81.3, 82.8, 82.29, 82.66; KI 54.8; PI 6.34-50; MC 4.15; MY 4.x+14; PI 9.72-73. See introduction 1.7. See guru, deśika, sthāpaka, and mantrin.
āya / āyu	In vāstuvīdyā passages, the term āya is used for a system whereby śalyas are discovered in the vāstu body according to the diurnal passage of the sun: BK vy 9-17; MY 4.x+7 – x+12. See introduction 2.14 and figure 28. (In prāsādalakṣaṇa passages, a different set of āyas or āyus is used to determine suitable measurements.)
ālaya	Temple. Usually as devālaya or surālaya: BK vy 111, 113, 126, 133, 137; KI 54.38. See prāsāda, dhāman and maṇḍira.
iṣṭaka	bricks are placed in the excavation under the building at the cardinal and intermediate points: DM 84.3. See śilā and vedī.
karṭṛ	the patron: BK vy 10; DM 79.34; MY 4.x+14, 4.y+10; PI 6.94, 8.34, 8.40, 9.60, 9.72-73, 9.75, 9.78, 9.89. See yajamāna and kāraka.
kāraka	the patron: PI 9.76, 9.82, 9.92. See yajamāna and karṭṛ.
kīlakā / kīlaka / kīla	1 pegs used to position the cords in mapping the building plan, and to mark the cardinal and intermediate points along the outer border of the plan: DM 80.98, 81.7 + footnote, 81.10-11, 81.25, 81.33-35, 81.38, 81.40. See the discussion in the footnote to DM 81.7c. See śaṅku. 2 a peg śalya: MY 4.x+20; PI 6.10, 9.83.
kumbha	1 pots, 5 or 9 in number, on which the śilās, stones are placed: DM 81.25, 82.37, 82.84, 84.40; MC 4.37; PI 6.64, 6.85. See introduction 2.12. 2 pots used in the lamp test for ground quality: PI 6.18. 3 a temple type: PI 8.103, 8.124, 8.155.
koṭṭa	a fortress: PI 8.212.
koṣṭha	a cell within the vāstu: BK vy 36, 110, 121, 140; KI 54.17, 54.19-21; PI 8.16, 8.22, 8.79, 8.114, 8.121, 8.134, 8.146-148, 8.169, 8.172, 8.186, 8.197. See introduction 2.5. See pada.
kṣetra	the area of ground marked out by sūtra lines as the site for the construction: BK vy 1, 7, 125, 127-129, 132; DM 76.1, 76.3, 76.17; DM 80.2, 80.99, 81.38, 82.24; KI 54.30; MC 4.4; MY 4.x+3, 4.x+13, 4.y+5;

	PI 8.1, 8.5, 8.8, 8.43, 8.72, 8.88, 8.103, 8.116, 8.120, 8.125, 8.130, 8.133, 8.143, 8.176, 8.207, 8.212, 9.2, 9.59. See introduction 2.1.
khāta	the excavation that underlies a building: DM 82.84, 82.86, 83.1-12, 83.16-17, 83.20, 84.27; MC 4.7, 4.31; PI 6.53, 6.60.
kheṭa(ka)	small settlement: BK vy 102; MC 4.6; PI 6.5, 8.90, 8.197, 8.206. See introduction 2.5.
garbha	1 the cella, the innermost chamber, of a temple, in which the image is housed, built over the central Brahmā position in the vāstu: DM 81.19; MC 4.42. 2 also a term for that central Brahmā position in the vāstu: BK vy 134; DM 82.6, 85.20, 86.11.
guru	chief officiant: DM 80.37, 82.15, 83.14, 83.19, 84.43; MY 4.x+2, 4.x+14, 4.y+14, 4.y+28; PI 6.64, 6.91, 6.95, 9.75. See introduction 1.7. See ācārya, deśika, sthāpaka and mantrin.
graha	"seizer": 1 the 8 demons around the outer edges of the vāstu: BK vy 113, 117; MY 4.y+3; PI 6.104, 8.94, 8.101, 8.128, 8.160-161, 8.198, 8.208, 8.248, 8.254, 9.106. Synonyms used are rākṣasa (e.g. at BK vy 117) and vetāla (e.g. at BK vy 141). 2 the planets: DM 78.7, 84.23; MY 4.x+12, 4.y+10; PI 8.58, 8.236-7, 8.246, 9.150.
grāma	small settlement: BK vy 102; DM 84.56; MC 4.6; PI 6.5, 8.90, 8.206, 8.211. See introduction 2.5.
chandas	1 In prāsādalakṣaṇa passages, this term is used in combination with tala and ūrdhva to describe plan and elevation. So talacchanda is the standard word for a plan and ūrdhvacchanda is the standard word for an elevation. 2 In the portions under examination in this study, the term is used to describe a building design or style. PI 8.93, 8.101.
jagatī/i(bandhaka)	the base on which temple is built. DM 81.5, 81.14, 81.16, 81.19 (jagati) 83.2, 85.2, 85.9, 85.16, 86.21. See piṇḍikā / piṇḍī, vedi and pīṭha.
jaṅghā	1 'shank', that portion of the temple between the base of the doorway and the base of the spire: PI 8.140. 2 the shank of the vāstupuruṣa: BK vy 12; DM 77.13; MY 4.x+10; PI 9.26, 9.48-51. 3 shank in general: DM 80.83, 80.95.

jīvasūtra	the term given to each half of each mūlasūtra, running to the centre of the plan from the outer edge in each cardinal direction. DM 81.17, 81.22, 86.6.
toraṇa	archway: PI 8.89. At DM 86.6-16 an account is given of toraṇas that are placed over the path of the cords in the cardinal directions. From the horizontal tops of these toraṇas verticals are hung down, to check the alignment of the cords.
dikśilā	See śilā.
diksūtra	cords in the cardinal directions (east-west and north-south), crossing at the centre of the plan. These cords are laid down in excavation base: DM 81.13, 83.6, 83.11, 83.14-16, 85.8, 85.24, all of chapter 86; PI 8.8.
durga	stronghold: BK vy 102.
deśa	district: BK vy 114c-120b, 121, 135; DM 82.17; MY 4.y+2; PI 8.90, 8.158, 8.167.
deśika	the chief officiant. See introduction 1.7. See ācārya, guru, sthāpaka and mantrin.
daivajña	the astrologer: DM 82.8-9, 82.14, 82.18, 82.21.
dravya	1 elements of the construction: DM 79.22, 79.24, 79.28, 79.33-34. 2 offering materials: BK vy 99, 150, 152; 82.27; PI 6.88. 3 śalya, extraneous matter: DM 80.43; MY 4.x+17; PI 9.96. 4 markings on the śilā: DM 84.8, 84.12.
dhāman	Temple: MY 4.y+1, 4.y+40. See ālaya, prāsāda and maṇḍira.
dhāra / dhārā	the outline of the construction; its outer edge: DM 84.32, 84.34, 85.3-4, 85.7, 85.10, 85.17, 86.19. See paridhi.
nagara	large settlement, city: BK vy 102; DM 84.56; PI 6.5, 8.90, 8.151-152, 8.228, 9.74.
nāḍī	cords (sūtras) laid over the vāstu: MY 4.y+14; PI 8.10-12, 8.19, 8.21, 8.29, 8.37, 8.143-144, 8.158-9, 8.197, 9.1, 9.3, 9.5-6. See introduction 2.6.
nemī	a boundary around the vāstu: PI 8.104-106b.
pattana	town: PI 8.185, 8.196.
pada	a cell within the vāstu: BK vy 19, 20-21, 23, 25-26, 31-32, 34-37, 41, 68, 90-93, 100-101, 104, 107, 109-116, 119, 123, 126, 128, 137-141; DM 76.1, 76.3-4, 76.14-16, 76.18-20, 76.23-24, 76.26, 79.4, 79.7, 79.9-10, 80.49, 82.25; KI 54.16-19, 54.30, 54.35-37; MC 4.19, 4.22; MY 4.y+3-4, 4.y+8, 4.y+10; PI 8.12, 8.15, 8.18, 8.22, 8.28, 8.33, 8.74-82, 8.91, 8.105-106, 8.118, 8.127, 8.145, 8.150, 8.159-161, 8.163-165, 8.167, 8.173, 8.186-187, 8.189-192, 8.194-196, 8.199, 8.204-205, 8.207, 8.210-217, 8.219-223, 8.225, 8.236-238, 8.243, 8.249, 8.256, 9.7-13, 9.15-16,

- 9.18, 9.21, 9.26, 9.32, 9.39-43, 9.47, 9.49, 9.51-52. See introduction 2.5.
See koṣṭha.
- parigraha an examination of the ground (bhū) or site (kṣetra) upon which construction will take place, selection of the ground / site, ritual appropriation of the ground / site: BK vy 7; KI 54.2; MC 4.1, 4.14 (parigrahet); MY 4.y+12; PI 6.1-2, 6.25, 6.51.
- paridhi the outline of the construction; its outer edge: DM 81.20, 81.24, 83.5, 84.36, 85.23; PI 8.123, 8.126, 8.133. See dhāra / dhārā.
- piṇḍikā/ piṇḍī a base for an image or temple: DM 85.23; MC 3.29; PI 8.198.
See pīṭha, vedī and jagatī.
- pīṭha a base for an image or temple: BK vy 107; DM 84.22, 85.5-6, 85.10-11, 85.13-18, 85.22-25, 86.1-3, 86.5, 86.10-11, 86.14, 86.19, 86.26; MC 4.41-42; PI 6.4, 8.136. See piṇḍikā / piṇḍī, vedī and jagatī.
- pura fortress: BK vy 102; PI 8.89-90.
city: MC 4.6.
a site on which one builds: BK vy 121.
- prā(g)grīvā a projection of the wall at the śukāghrā: DM 81.19, 83.2, 85.2, 85.9. See śukāghrā.
- prāsāda temple, palace: DM 80.3, 81.3-4, 81.13-14, 81.16, 81.18, 81.21-24, 83.16, 83.21, 83.23, 84.3, 84.21, 84.26, 84.49, 84.53, 84.56, 85.2, 85.7-8, 85.11, 85.13-14, 85.16, 86.18, 86.21, 86.26; KI 54.1, 54.57; MC 4.41; PI 6.1-2, 6.60, 6.82, 6.97, 6.104, 6.107, 8.89, 8.91, 9.162. See ālaya, dhāman and maṇḍira.
- brahmākhyā kumbha a pot placed over the brahmasthāna in the excavation: DM 82.37-42.
- brahmaśilā the stone placed over the brahmasthāna, at the centre of the vāstu: BK vy 106; MC 3.29-35; DM 85.18, 85.20-21; PI 6.67, 8.89, 8.92.
- brahmasūtra a cord running through the Brahmā position at the centre of the site: DM 83.1, 85.25, 86.23; PI 8.104, 8.113. See madhyasūtra. At DM 86.20-23, it appears that the brahmasūtra and the madhyasūtra refer to the same cord, running through the centre (madhya) of the site, at the Brahmā position.
- brahmasthāna the position at the centre of the vāstu plan, governed by Brahmā: DM 79.23, 82.31, 82.37, 82.41, 82.57, 83.10, 83.20, 83.22; PI 8.7, 8.20.
- bhāraguru base rubble in the foundation?: PI 6.54.
- maṭha a residence for ascetics: BK vy 102; PI 8.90.

maṇḍapa	an open hall or pavilion: BK vy 126; DM 81.4, 81.19, 83.2, 85.2, 85.9, 86.22; MY 4.y+13; PI 8.141.
maṇḍala	province: Bk vy 120, 134; PI 8.168, 8.184.
maṇḍira	Temple, palace: BK vy 108, 111; KI 54.38. See prāsāda, dhāman and ālaya.
matsya / matsa	the fish-shaped figure made by the intersection of two arcs in the setting up of a building plan: BK vy 125; DM 81.15, 83.7-8, 83.12, 83.18-19, 85.8, 86.5-6, 86.15-18, 86.25. See mīna.
madhyasūtra	the cords that run through the centre of the site, north-south and east-west: DM 81.21, 81.23, 82.86, 85.2, 85.7, 86.20, 86.26. See brahmasūtra. At DM 86.20-23, it appears that the brahmasūtra and the madhyasūtra refer to the same cord, running through the centre (madhya) of the site, at the Brahmā position.
mantrin	the chief officiant: DM 81.11, 82.27, 82.32, 82.41, 82.69, 82.71-72, 82.74, 82.84, 84.36, 84.39. See introduction 1.7. See ācārya, guru, deśika and sthāpaka.
marman	a vulnerable point in the building plan: BK vy 142, 144; DM 78.15, 79.1, 79.7-8, 79.12, 79.18, 79.20, 79.23-25, 79.28-30, 79.34, 79.36-38, 80.14, 80.100; KI 54.22-23, 54.38; MC 4.26-27; PI 6.93, 8.5, 8.19, 8.21, 8.29-31, 8.38, 8.41, 8.114, 8.118, 8.122, 8.127, 8.135, 8.146, 8.167, 8.184, 8.196, 8.205, 8.211, 8.226, 8.228, 8.246, 8.256, 9.22, 9.27, 9.53-58, 9.60-61, 9.65, 9.105. See introduction 2.7.
maṣṭilā	chalk: DM 81.10, 81.25, 81.27.
mīna	the fish-shaped figure made by the intersection of two arcs in the setting up of a building plan: BK vy 127. See matsya / matsa.
mūrtipa	an assistant to the chief officiant. There are 8 mūrtipas. DM 81.33 (aṣṭau).
mūlapāda / mūlapādu	The foundation: DM 84.1, 84.3, 84.20, 84.22, 85.1-10, 85.25.
mūlapādacaya / mūlacaya	The construction of the foundation: DM 84. 56-7.
mūlasūtra	The two principal cords (sūtras) that are used to mark out a building plan. One runs east-west through the centre; the other runs north-south through the centre: DM 81.17-19, possibly also at 81.27.
yajamāna	1 the patron: DM 80.4, 80.37, 82.7-8, 84.24. See kartṛ and kāraka. 2 one of the 8 mūrtis (see introduction 1.7): PI 6.81.
yava	barley grain, a unit of linear measure: DM 79.12, MC 3.32-33, 4.26.

- rajju cords (sūtras) laid over the vāstu: BK vy 108-109, 114, 119, 123-124, 141; MC 4.19; MY 4.y+1, 4.y+8; PI 8.14, 8.17, 8.19, 8.23, 8.28-29, 8.37, 8.67, 8.72, 8.109, 8.114, 8.118, 8.122, 8.127, 8.130, 8.135, 8.145, 8.166, 8.183, 8.195, 8.205, 8.210, 8.225, 8.228, 8.255, 9.21. See introduction 2.6.
- ratha(ka) the projections outward horizontally of the walls: DM 83.2, 85.2, 85.9, 85.16.
- raśmi / raśmin cords (sūtras) laid over the vāstu. BK vy 119. See introduction 2.6.
- lagna 1 the intersection of the east-west and north-south lines in the centre of the building site: DM 82.14, 82.19-22, 84.34.
2 an auspicious moment: MC 4.14, PI 6.29.
- vaṃśa cords (sūtra) laid over the vāstu. DM 79.1-4, 79.6 (anuvaṃśa), 79.9, 79.11-12, 79.17, 79.31; KI 54.38; MC 4.19; PI 8.13, 8.114, 8.166. See introduction 2.6.
- vāstu The kṣetra construction area is termed the vāstu when it is treated as a domain ritually inhabited by a vāstupuruṣa and the deities of the vāstu. BK vy 1, 17, 19, 25, 26, 28, 93, 98, 100, 106-108, 114, 120-123, 133, 134, 136, 137; DM 76.2, 76.7, 76.12, 76.16, 76.18, 76.25-26, 77.1-2, 77.13, 77.15-16, 78.1, 78.13-15, 79.1, 79.7-8, 79.35, 79.38, 80.1-2, 80.4, 80.11, 80.14, 80.16, 80.18, 80.20, 80.26, 80.33, 80.36-37, 80.39, 80.42, 80.45, 80.90, 80.99, 81.1, 81.7, 82.6, 82.23, 82.25, 82.27, 82.36, 82.46, 82.52, 82.57-58, 82.61, 82.71, 82.85, 83.1, 83.4, 83.20, 84, 26, 84.34, 84.53-54; KI 54.24, 54.29, 54.39, 54.47; MC 4.20-21, 4.23-24, 4.26-27, 4.39; MY 4.x+3, 4.x+4, 4.x+6, 4.y+11, 4.y+14; PI 6.23, 6.60-62, 6.65, 6.93, 8.1, 8.5, 8.28, 8.41, 8.86-88, 8.91, 8.95, 8.98-100, 8.110-112, 8.116, 8.119-120, 8.122, 8.124, 8.128-9, 8.131-132, 8.135, 8.137-138, 8.151, 8.158, 8.168, 8.185, 8.197, 8.206, 8.224, 8.228, 8.236, 8.246, 8.248, 8.257; 9.1, 9.33, 9.36, 9.56-7, 9.59-60, 9.62-65, 9.69, 9.75, 9.101, 9.105-106, 9.139, 9.150. See introduction 2.1.
- vāstuyāga the ritual of the building plan: BK vy 1; DM 76.25, 81.1, 82.85.
- vāstunara/ vāstupuruṣa / vāstudeha / vāstuśarīra the man of the building plan: BK vy 17, 25-26, 98, 106, 133, 136; DM 77.2, 77.16, 78.13-14, 79.35, 80.2, 80.4, 80.16, 80.90, 82.36, 82.58; KI 54.39; MC 4.24; MY 4.x+3, 4.y+14; PI 6.65. See introduction 2.1.
- vitasti a unit of linear measure, the distance between the extended tips of the thumb and little finger, or between the tip of the middle finger and the wrist, = 12 aṅgulas: DM 80.87; KI 54.46.
- viśvakarman the divine architect: DM 78.8, 81.11-12, 81.25, 82.9.
- vṛttamastaka a turning of the top layer of the foundation?: PI 6.59.
- vedī 1 a piece of ground established as a base for ritual procedure: DM 84.27; MY 4.y+13 (vedikā).

	2	stones placed in the excavation under the building at the cardinal and intermediate points: PI 6.6, 6.70. See śilā and iṣṭaka.
śakuna	3	a base for an image: PI 8.139. See piṇḍikā / piṇḍī, pīṭha and jagatī. a bird, or an omen in general: DM 80.2, 80.12, 80.34-35, 84.34; PI 6.25, 6.41, 6.45-46, 6.48, 6.50, 6.61, 9.70 (śakuniśakuna), 9.74. See discussion at DM 80.2.
śaṅku	1	pegs used to position the cords in mapping the building plan, and to mark the cardinal and intermediate points along the outer border of the plan: DM 81.24, 81.27, 81.30, 81.32-33, 81.36-37, 81.39, 82.30, 82.58. See the discussion in the footnote to DM 81.7c. See kīlakā.
	2	the gnomon used to determine the east-west line: DM 82.19-21, 86.3; MC 4.16; PI 8.6-7.
śalya		extraneous material in the building site: Bk vy 5, 8-10, 13-15, 17; DM 79.38, 80.1-2, 80.4, 80.8-12, 80.14-17, 80.20, 80.23, 80.36, 80.38-39, 80.42-45, 80.49-50, 80.52-53, 80.55-57, 80.60-61, 80.64-65, 80.67-69, 80.71-73, 80.77-82, 80.84-85, 80.88-97, 80.101; KI 54.1, 54.39-41, 47; MC 4.1, 4.29-30; MY 4.x+1-4, 4.x+7, 4.x+10, 4.x+12-13; PI 6.61, 9.57, 9.62, 9.68-70, 9.74, 9.76-77, 9.79, 9.81-82, 9.84, 9.88-91, 9.99, 9.101-104. See introduction 2.9.
śilā		stones are placed in the excavation under the building at the centre and the cardinal and intermediate points: BK vy 106; DM 83.9-11, 83.13, 83.19, 83.23, all of chapter 84; 85.1, 85.3, 85.18-22; MC 3.29-35, 4.32, 4.37; PI 6.64, 6.67, 6.80, 6.90-91, 6.94, 8.89, 8.92. See introduction 2.12. See vedī and iṣṭaka.
śilpin		an artisan: BK vy 6; DM 82.23, 84.27, 84.30, 84.36; KI 54.8; MC 4.15.
śukāghrā		[parrot] beak, a projection from the śikhara, supported by a projection at the wall termed the prā(g)grīva: the term is not seen in the passages treated in this study.
sirā / śirā		cords (sūtras) laid over the vāstu: BK vy 114, 124; DM 78.15, 79.1-2, 79.9, 79.15-16, 79.23, 79.38, 80.100; KI 54.22, 54.38; MY 4.y+2. See introduction 2.6.
suṣira		ventilation shaft: PI 8.136, 8.232.
sūtra (sūtrita, sūtrayet)		a cord. Cords are used in marking out the building plan and in measuring the elements of the elevation: BK vy 106, 108, 128, 144; DM 79.3, 80.2-3, 80.5, 80.7-9, 80.18-19, 80.24, 80.28-29, 80.98, 80.101, 81.1, 81.3, 81.7, 81.10, 81.12-23, 81.26, 81.38-40, 82.9, 82.14, 82.22,

	82.83, 82.86, 83.1, 83.6-7, 83.11-12, 83.14-17, 83.19-23, 84.31-32, 85.2-3, 85.7-8, 85.10, 85.24-25, 86.1, 86.5-7, 86.11-14, 86.16, 86.19-26; KI 54.8, 54.21-22; MC 4.15, 4.17, 4.28, 4.32; PI 6.62; See introduction 2.6 and brahmasūtra, madhyasūtra, diksūtra, mūlasūtra, and jīvasūtra.
sopāna	set of steps: PI 8.231.
sthapati	the architect: BK vy 10; DM 80.37, 81.3, 81.29, 82.8-9, 82.18; MY 4.x+14.
sthāpaka	the chief officiant: DM 82.10, 82.18, 82.22; 84.25, 84.30, 84.36; PI 8.40. See introduction 1.7. See ācārya, guru, deśika and mantrin.
harmya	palace: BK vy 103.
hasta	'hand', a unit of linear measure (from elbow to tip of middle finger) = 24 aṅgulas: DM 80.70, 80.72, 80.75, 80.78, 80.81-83, 81.18, 81.22, 84.4, 84.14, 86.8-9; KI 54.40-45; MC 4.33; MY 4.x+15, 4.x+17-21; PI 6.11, 6.53, 6.57, 6.70.
hastipāda(ka)	mallet for pounding earth down: BK vy 5, PI 6.58.